

LINGUICOGNITIVE ANALYSIS OF PHRASES FORMED WITH THE USE OF BLACK AND WHITE COLORS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the linguocognitive properties of phrases based on the colors “white” and “black” in the Uzbek language. It reveals how the names of colors carry meaning not only semantically, but also cognitively. In the process of analysis, it is revealed that the expressions created using these colors reflect the worldview, values, and cultural consciousness of the people. The article also analyzes metaphorical thinking and conceptual contradictions based on color (for example: white - light, black - darkness) at the level of linguistic units.

Keywords: linguocognitive analysis, phraseology, black and white colors, conceptual opposition, folk thinking, colors semantics.

Entrance: Language is not only a means of communication, but also the main mirror of the thinking, psyche and cultural memory of the people. Colors have a special place in the internal structure of each language. Colors are firmly established in the human mind not only as visual images, but also through spiritual-spiritual, emotional and symbolic concepts. In particular, the colors “white” and “black” are distinguished by a strong semantic and cognitive load in most peoples. In the Uzbek language, many expressions, proverbs, sayings and phraseological units have been formed based on these colors, which embody the values, aesthetic views, worldview and life experiences of the people. This article studies expressions involving the colors “white” and “black” based on a linguocognitive approach. That is, not only the lexical and grammatical structure of expressions, but also the conceptual content behind them, their resonance in the thinking of the people, mental associations and spiritual symbols are analyzed. This serves to provide a deeper understanding of ancient perceptions and life experiences in the minds of the people through the names of colors in the language.

Methodology

Shavkat Rahmatullayev's “Explanatory Phraseological Dictionary of the Uzbek Language” lists several forms of the expression “oq-u qora”, “oq-qora” and their explanations:

To recognize black and white. To recognize black and white.
To understand black and white. To recognize black and white

To distinguish between black and white. To distinguish between black and white

To understand between black and white. To recognize black and white

To distinguish between black and white. To distinguish between black and white

To know between black and white. To recognize black and white
To distinguish between black and white. To distinguish between good and evil, between benefit and harm. Version: to distinguish between black and white, between what; to distinguish between black and white, to distinguish between black and white. Similar: to recognize black and white.

To recognize black and white. To know good and evil, between benefit and harm, to have life experience. Version: to recognize black and white, to recognize black and white, to know black and white, to know black and white, to understand black and white. Similar: to distinguish between black and white [1,197-198].

We often encounter expressions formed using the colors “white” and “black” in works of art. For example, we can also see the symbolic meaning of white and black in the chapter “White Marble, Black Marble” of O’tkir Khashimov’s story “The Works of the World” dedicated to mothers:

Spring does not begin at the sun-drenched foot of the walls. Spring does not begin at the sunny banks of the ditches. Spring begins at the cemetery. The first grass sprouts from the sides of the gloomy, covered graves. The first poplars ring their mournful bells over the silent cemetery. The rich red roses are the first to bloom here. Who knows, perhaps this is the only blessing that nature shows the souls of the deceased once a year... Among the red roses glowing like embers, among the lined up glass vases, marble stones are visible. White marble, black marble, blue marble...

Before analyzing this passage, let’s pay attention to its title. Why did the author name the story “White Marble, Black Marble”? What is its symbolic meaning? The author’s purpose in giving the title “White Marble, Black Marble” is that marble is a strong, long-lasting stone. “White” and “black” marbles are symbols of indelible memory, constant love, sadness and respect in the human heart. That is, the author emphasizes that through the images of marble, the endless love for the mother and the suffering born of losing her life forever in the heart. Now let’s analyze the sentence white marble, black marble, blue marble... presented in the passage. Here, the combinations “white marble” and

“black marble” are used together, symbolizing human memory, loyalty and eternity.

“White marble” – memory, purity, love;

“Black marble” – painful, but lasting and enduring memory.

These are used not as simple building materials, but as the concept of eternal memory that lives in the human heart. That is, in the heart of every person, the mother's soul is like a monument built of white marble, but at the bottom of this monument there lives a grief that is as heavy as black marble, but leaves a lasting mark. In general, through the colors of white and black, the author symbolically illuminates the idea of the mother's image, mother's memory, and human values. Through these linguocognitive images, abstract concepts formed in the people's thinking are given a concrete form through language [2,144].

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that phrases involving the colors white and black appear as linguistic units with a deep meaning, symbolic and cognitive load in the human mind, whose language and thinking are inextricably linked. Based on the linguocognitive approach, it can be observed that white is usually associated with the concepts of purity, goodness, and positivity, while black is associated with. However, in some cases, these colors acquire an abstract, poetic, or even positive-symbolic meaning depending on their context. Therefore, phraseological units, artistic expressions, and images involving white and black serve as an important tool for creating meaning in language, creating images, and increasing the emotional impact based on the conceptual map formed in human thinking. Therefore, the linguocognitive study of these phrases is relevant for such branches of linguistics as semantics, cultural studies, and psycholinguistics.

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